

GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF FRUITS AND VEGETABLES IN INDIA

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Abstract

The paper attempts to explore the growth performance of fruits and vegetables in India state-wise. The secondary data were collected from the period 2001-2021 and the data were analysed using the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) using the exponential model and the student 't' test was employed to test the significance of the growth rates of fruits and vegetables. The study is divided into two periods: Period I (2001-2011) and Period II (2011-2021). The study revealed that during the period of 20 years i.e. 2001 - 2021 the growth rate of area, production and productivity of fruits at India level was significantly increased at the rate of 23.115, 41.557 and 14.979 per cent respectively. In the growth rates the states which showed highest significantly positive growth rate were Chhattisgarh at the rate of 206.349, 160.988 per cent in area and production of fruits, respectively. And Uttar Pradesh at the rate of 43.622 per cent in productivity of fruits. During the period of 20 years i.e. 2001 - 2021 the growth rate of area, production, productivity of vegetables at India level was significantly increased at the rate of 24.750, 38.157 and 10.747 per cent, respectively. In the growth rates the states which showed highest significantly positive growth rate were Madhya Pradesh at the rate of 127.476 per cent in area and Madhya Pradesh at the rate of 172.355 per cent in production of vegetables and Arunachal Pradesh at the rate of 54.055 per cent in productivity of vegetables.

Keywords: Growth, Fruits, Vegetables, Area, Production, Productivity

Introduction

Agricultural growth has been a subject of significant discussion in the economic literature of India. Growth performance in agricultural production is a major factor contributing to price volatility in agricultural products. This, in turn, has serious implications for food management, food security, and economic stability within a country. So the present study has been undertaken to evaluate the growth performance of fruits and vegetables in India and the states of India for the period of 2001 - 2021 (20 years). The time-series data of area, production and productivity of fruits and vegetables for the years of 2001 - 2021 were used for the analysis.

Methodology

Growth rates in area, production and productivity of fruits and vegetables were analysed at state level along with the country. Secondary time series data were used for estimating the above-mentioned objectives for the years from 2001-11 to 2011-21. Growth rate was computed for two sub-periods and overall period. Period-I consisted from the year 2001 to 2011. Period-II was from the year 2011 to 2021 and overall period comprises from the year 2001-2021.

The compound growth rate serves as a key indicator for measuring agricultural growth and can be applied to predict the area, production, productivity, and other aspects of various agricultural commodities. It holds significant importance in agricultural policy-making, making it crucial to obtain precise estimates of the growth rate to inform suitable policies effectively. The accuracy of the estimated growth rate heavily depends on employing appropriate statistical procedures during the estimation process. The compound growth rate is essentially a compounding of annual growth rates over a specific period. When dealing with data that exhibits constant returns, such as in fixed deposits, calculating the compound growth rate between two data points is straightforward. However, in case where annual growth rates vary and follow monotonically increasing or decreasing patterns, the compound growth rate is determined by fitting a non-linear model, particularly the exponential model. The exponential model is widely used in economic analysis. Traditionally, the compound growth rates were estimated by converting the growth model to a semi-logarithmic form and then using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique, assuming a multiplicative error term.

$$Y_t = b_0 * (b_1)^t * e_t$$

$$\ln(Y_t) = b_0 + t * \ln b_1 + e_t$$

Where,

$\ln(Y_t)$ is the natural logarithm of time series data for area / production / yield for year t
 b_0 is the constant term

t is the time trends for years of interest

e_t is the error term

b_1 is growth rate for the period under consideration (i.e. slope coefficient).

Then, Compound growth rate of exponential model was calculated using following equation

$$\text{Compound Growth Rate} = [(Antilog b_1) - 1] * 100$$

Where,

b -regression coefficient of t on Y

The student 't' test was employed to test the significance of the growth rates at both 5% and 1% level of significance.

Result and discussion**The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables of period-I (2001-2011)**

The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables in area, production and productivity during the period-I of study i.e. 2001-2011 is presented in the Table 1.

In area, all India level showed a positive growth of 27.158 per cent in fruits and a positive growth rate of 14.938 per cent in vegetables. In area, in case of fruits Chhattisgarh showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 237.286 per cent and Uttar Pradesh showed lowest significantly growth rate by 9.939 per cent. In case of vegetables Chhattisgarh showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 100.366 per cent and West Bengal showed lowest significantly positive growth rate by 7.650 per cent.

In production, all India level showed a positive growth of 30.073 and 22.666 per cent in both fruits and vegetables respectively. In production, in case of fruits Chhattisgarh showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 125.365 per cent in production of fruits and Bihar showed lowest significantly negative growth rate by 11.169 per cent and in case of vegetables Mizoram showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 78.422 per cent and Nagaland showed highest significantly negative growth rate by -37.882 per cent.

In productivity, all India level showed a positive growth of 2.293 and 6.723 per cent in both fruits and vegetables respectively. In productivity, in case of fruits Mizoram showed highest significantly

positive growth rate by 66.154 per cent and Chhattisgarh showed highest significant negative growth rate by -33.183 per cent. In case of vegetables Arunachal Pradesh showed highest significantly positive

growth rate by 33.819 per cent and Nagaland showed highest significantly negative growth rate by -21.580 per cent.

Table 1: The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables (2001-2011)

STATE	STUDY PERIOD (2001- 2011)					
	AREA		PRODUCTION		PRODUCTIVITY	
	Fruits	Vegetables	Fruits	Vegetables	Fruits	Vegetables
Andhra Pradesh	20.285**	36.535**	33.965**	70.532**	11.373**	24.900**
Arunachal Pradesh	27.244**	-36.148 NS	0.677 NS	-14.554 NS	-20.879**	33.819*
Assam	10.597*	11.125 NS	14.928*	22.728 NS	3.917 NS	10.441 NS
Bihar	1.474 NS	18.340**	11.169*	30.594**	9.555**	10.355**
Chhattisgarh	237.286**	100.366**	125.365**	70.687**	-33.183*	-14.812 NS
Gujarat	44.925**	39.769**	67.888**	59.280**	-11.648NS	13.959**
Haryana	13.844 NS	44.381**	11.965*	39.711**	-1.651 NS	-3.234 NS
Himachal Pradesh	0.875 NS	41.735**	36.544*	42.427**	35.359 NS	0.488 NS
Jammu and Kashmir	33.969**	33.796*	32.238**	66.271**	-1.292 NS	24.272**
Jharkhand	30.932*	35.990**	32.830**	66.413**	1.450 NS	22.372**
Karnataka	16.986**	13.285**	20.756**	43.625**	3.223**	26.782**
Kerala	29.802*	22.602**	48.753*	19.558**	14.600*	-2.483 NS
Madhya Pradesh	45.212*	40.536**	53.731*	39.389**	5.867 NS	-0.817 NS
Maharashtra	58.966**	12.857*	9.150**	19.790*	-31.337**	6.144 NS
Manipur	28.043*	25.557*	40.669**	68.147**	9.860 NS	33.921**
Meghalaya	25.283**	11.511*	23.221**	18.161**	-1.646 NS	5.963*
Mizoram	26.617**	25.440 NS	110.379**	78.422*	66.154*	42.237 NS
Nagaland	5.676 NS	-20.788 NS	1.250 NS	-37.882*	-4.188 NS	-21.580*
Odisha	15.322**	0.083 NS	11.187 NS	6.580**	-3.586 NS	6.492**
Punjab	34.180**	14.496**	55.783**	21.026**	16.100**	5.703 NS
Rajasthan	33.740**	18.602**	82.836**	52.256**	36.710**	28.376**
Sikkim	33.740**	30.830**	47.296**	40.909**	39.968**	7.704**
Tamil Nadu	19.056**	20.956**	44.834**	31.983**	21.652**	9.116**
Tripura	15.506**	0.843 NS	11.794**	10.714 NS	-3.214*	9.788*
Uttar Pradesh	9.939*	8.895**	36.852*	15.081**	24.479*	5.680*
Uttarakhand	25.930 NS	4.697 NS	32.858**	34.184*	5.501 NS	28.164**
West Bengal	18.013**	7.650**	24.197**	15.015*	5.240*	6.842 NS
ALL INDIA	27.158**	14.938**	30.073**	22.666**	2.293 NS	6.723*

Note: ** - significant at 1%, * - significant at 5 %, NS - non- significant.

The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables of period-II (2011-2021)

The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables in area, production and productivity during the overall period of study i.e. 2011-2021 is presented in the Table 2.

In area, all India level showed a negative growth of -1.287 per cent in fruits and a positive growth rate of 7.830 per cent in vegetables. In area, in case of fruits Madhya Pradesh showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 55.616 per cent and Maharashtra showed highest significantly negative growth rate by -32.528 per cent. In case of vegetables Madhya Pradesh showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 8.139 per cent and Andhra Pradesh showed highest significant negative growth rate by -29.929 per cent.

In production, all India level showed a positive growth of 14.099 and 10.291 per cent in both fruits and vegetables respectively. In

production, in case of fruits Haryana showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 55.165 per cent and Arunachal Pradesh showed highest significantly negative growth rate by -40.633 per cent and in case of vegetables Madhya Pradesh showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 35.779 per cent and Arunachal Pradesh showed highest significantly negative growth rate by -50.527 per cent.

In productivity, all India level showed a positive growth of 15.586 and 2.282 per cent in both fruits and vegetables respectively. In productivity, in case of fruits Maharashtra showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 53.463 per cent and Arunachal Pradesh showed highest significantly negative growth rate by -16.619 per cent. In case of vegetables Rajasthan showed highest significantly positive growth rate by 40.383 per cent and Arunachal Pradesh showed highest significantly negative growth rate by -43.523 per cent.

Table 2: The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables (2011-2021)

STATE	STUDY PERIOD (2011- 2021)					
	AREA		PRODUCTION		PRODUCTIVITY	
	Fruits	Vegetables	Fruits	Vegetables	Fruits	Vegetables

	Fruits	Vegetables	Fruits	Vegetables	Fruits	Vegetables
Andhra Pradesh	6.153 NS	-29.929**	32.011**	-12.137*	24.358**	25.391**
Arunachal Pradesh	-28.800**	-12.403 NS	-40.633**	-50.527**	-16.619*	-43.523*
Assam	0.649 NS	6.056**	7.203**	5.660 NS	6.512**	-0.374 NS
Bihar	5.236*	0.481 NS	6.710*	2.937 NS	1.400 NS	2.444 NS
Chhattisgarh	9.711**	19.724**	27.035**	23.690**	15.791**	3.313**
Gujarat	9.790**	13.214**	7.275**	14.672**	-2.291 NS	1.287*
Haryana	20.917**	5.280 NS	55.165**	15.044**	28.323**	9.274**
Himachal Pradesh	4.205**	4.427*	17.582 NS	9.146**	12.837 NS	4.518**
Jammu and Kashmir	-10.842**	-3.465*	7.532 NS	-2.862 NS	20.608**	0.625 NS
Jharkhand	10.334**	2.400 NS	18.143**	-7.469*	7.077*	-9.637**
Karnataka	5.004**	0.063 NS	6.616**	0.137 NS	1.535 NS	0.075 NS
Kerala	-0.692 NS	-20.383**	-13.272*	-13.682 NS	-12.668 NS	8.416 NS
Madhya Pradesh	55.616**	37.803**	41.714**	35.779**	-8.933 NS	-1.469 NS
Maharashtra	-32.528**	21.654**	3.545 NS	24.895**	53.463**	2.664 NS
Manipur	-5.958 NS	41.958**	4.828 NS	32.709**	11.470**	-6.515 NS
Meghalaya	6.301**	11.997**	12.413**	14.248**	5.750*	2.010 NS
Mizoram	18.443**	-0.407 NS	9.981**	-9.553 NS	-7.144**	-9.184 NS
Nagaland	-0.440 NS	18.514**	-0.525 NS	46.315**	-0.085 NS	23.458**
Odisha	2.913*	-3.820**	7.981**	-4.000*	4.924**	-0.187 NS
Punjab	17.186**	22.892**	21.507**	22.601**	3.687**	-0.237 NS
Rajasthan	21.365*	-4.146 NS	24.075**	34.562**	2.233 NS	40.383**
Sikkim	20.195**	7.875 NS	54.557**	20.825 NS	28.584*	12.004*
Tamil Nadu	-3.848 NS	-3.709 NS	-17.222**	-11.021*	-13.909**	-7.593**
Tripura	-2.884 NS	11.119**	-10.272 NS	15.155**	-7.607**	3.632**
Uttar Pradesh	23.841**	26.990**	44.562**	24.879**	16.732**	-1.662 NS
Uttarakhand	-5.011*	5.646*	-9.347**	-2.868 NS	-4.566**	-8.059**
West Bengal	12.817**	5.091**	11.735**	9.248*	-0.959 NS	3.956 NS
ALL INDIA	-1.287 NS	7.830**	14.099**	10.291**	15.586**	2.282 NS

Note: ** - significant at 1%, * - significant at 5 %, ^{NS} - non- significant.

The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables of overall period (2001-2021)

The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables in area, production and productivity during the overall period of study i.e. 2001-2021 is presented in the Table 3.

In area, all India level showed a positive growth of 23.115 per cent in fruits and a positive growth rate of 24.750 per cent in vegetables. In area, in case of fruits of fruits Chhattisgarh showed highest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 206.349 per cent and Bihar showed lowest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 5.301 per cent. In case of vegetables Madhya Pradesh showed highest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 127.476 per cent and Arunachal Pradesh showed highest significantly negative growth rate i.e. -65.803 per cent.

In production, all India level showed a positive growth of 41.557 and 38.157 per cent in both fruits and vegetables respectively. In

Table 3: The growth rates of the states between fruits and vegetables (2001-2021)

STATE	STUDY PERIOD (2001- 2021)					
	AREA		PRODUCTION		PRODUCTIVITY	
	Fruits	Vegetables	Fruits	Vegetables	Fruits	Vegetables
Andhra Pradesh	16.712**	33.375**	49.099**	81.573**	27.750**	36.137**
Arunachal Pradesh	14.197*	-65.803**	28.557*	-47.318**	12.574 NS	54.055**
Assam	19.591**	11.975**	30.000**	14.307*	8.704**	2.082 NS

production, in case of fruits Chhattisgarh showed highest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 160.988 per cent and Maharashtra showed lowest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 9.228 per cent and in case of vegetables Madhya Pradesh showed highest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 172.355 per cent and Arunachal Pradesh showed highest significantly negative growth rate i.e. -47.318 per cent.

In productivity, all India level showed a positive growth of 14.979 and 10.747 per cent in both fruits and vegetables respectively. In productivity, in case of fruits Uttar Pradesh showed highest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 43.622 per cent and Tripura showed highest significantly negative growth rate i.e. -17.750 per cent. In case of vegetables Arunachal Pradesh showed highest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 54.055 per cent. Uttar Pradesh showed lowest significantly positive growth rate i.e. 5.308 per cent.

Bihar	5.301**	11.727**	19.482**	24.892**	13.467**	11.783**
Chhattisgarh	206.349**	106.174**	160.988**	103.797**	-14.807*	-1.153 ^{NS}
Gujarat	43.917**	52.973**	67.018**	78.173**	16.052**	16.473**
Haryana	42.729**	46.277**	86.239**	57.987**	30.484**	8.005**
Himachal Pradesh	7.258**	37.421**	22.864*	46.494**	14.550 ^{NS}	6.602**
Jammu and Kashmir	51.495**	21.292**	42.124**	48.273**	-6.186 ^{NS}	22.245**
Jharkhand	74.185**	38.454**	76.307**	41.948**	1.218 ^{NS}	2.523 ^{NS}
Karnataka	26.009**	11.125**	31.554**	36.469**	4.400**	22.807**
Kerala	17.653**	0.113 ^{NS}	27.952**	-0.845 ^{NS}	8.754 ^{NS}	-0.957 ^{NS}
Madhya Pradesh	151.601**	127.476**	145.619**	172.355**	-2.377 ^{NS}	19.729**
Maharashtra	2.876 ^{NS}	34.390**	9.228**	51.680**	6.174 ^{NS}	12.865**
Manipur	22.134**	75.927**	58.367**	105.079**	29.666**	16.571**
Meghalaya	27.121**	13.804**	38.467**	30.029**	8.926**	14.257**
Mizoram	73.208**	180.203**	136.251**	147.448**	36.397**	-11.690 ^{NS}
Nagaland	58.991**	71.003**	85.554**	90.456**	16.707 ^{NS}	11.375 ^{NS}
Odisha	20.843**	0.515 ^{NS}	30.005**	8.285**	7.582**	7.730**
Punjab	43.570**	26.339**	73.355**	39.779**	20.746**	10.638**
Rajasthan	52.328**	27.239**	89.667**	81.301**	24.512**	42.489**
Sikkim	32.761**	34.858**	92.016**	54.970**	44.641**	14.913**
Tamil Nadu	14.551**	16.518**	17.945**	17.211**	2.964 ^{NS}	0.595 ^{NS}
Tripura	40.122**	19.985**	15.251**	46.940**	-17.750**	22.465**
Uttar Pradesh	25.080**	20.905**	79.642**	27.323**	43.622**	5.308**
Uttarakhand	21.290*	14.789**	15.763**	22.944**	-4.557 ^{NS}	7.104 ^{NS}
West Bengal	25.538**	9.618**	31.042**	20.859**	4.384**	10.255**
ALL INDIA	23.115**	24.750**	41.557**	38.157**	14.979**	10.747**

Note: ** - significant at 1%, * - significant at 5%, ^{NS} - non-significant.

Conclusion

1. During the period of 20 years i.e. 2001 - 2021, the growth rate of area of fruits in India level was significantly increased at the rate of 23.115 per cent. The growth rate of production was significantly increased at the rate of 41.557 per cent and productivity of fruits in India was significantly decreased at the rate of 14.979 per cent.

2. In growth rates the states which showed highest significantly positive growth rate are Chhattisgarh at the rate of 206.349 per cent in area of fruits, Chhattisgarh at the rate of 160.988 per cent in production of fruits and Uttar Pradesh at the rate of 43.622 per cent in productivity of fruits.

3. During the period of 20 years i.e. 2001 – 2021 the growth rate of area, production, productivity of vegetables in India level was significantly increased at the rate of 24.750, 38.157 and 10.747 per cent, respectively.

4. In growth rates the states which showed highest significantly positive growth rate were Madhya Pradesh at the rate of 127.476 per cent in area and Madhya Pradesh at the rate of 172.355 per cent in production of vegetables and Arunachal Pradesh at the rate of 54.055 per cent in productivity of vegetables.

5. The study concluded that the growth rate area of fruits is decreasing in India level while compare to production and growth rate of area in fruits is increasing compare to productivity of fruits.

6. In the case of vegetables, the growth rate of area is lesser than the production and growth rate of area is greater than the productivity.

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